

Covid -19 Pandemic Disease

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ABSTRACT

ARTICLE DETAILS

of infection with appropriate measures.

Covid-19 is one of the pandemic diseases which was widely spread all over the world. Now the new mutated variant strain, Delta plus, may cause a third wave of the coronavirus. So, all of them are worried about the current situation. SARS-CoV-2 is the virus cause Covid -19 disease. The important Clinical manifestation is loss of taste and smell, dry cough, and sore throat. Widely increasing mortality and morbidity more rapidly. So, we should prevent this spread

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KEYWORDS: Covid-19, Mutated virus, Pandemic, SARS-CoV-2, RT-PCR test.

INTRODUCTION

The name “*corona virus*” was coined in 1968, by June Almeida and David Tyrrell. These viruses were characterized by Solar Corona, like projection that’s called spikes which is on their surface. The word is derived from the ‘corona’ like or crown-like morphology observed in the electron microscope also looks like a single-stranded RNA genomic structure. In 1975, the coronaviridae family was established by the international committee on the taxonomy of viruses (ICTV). Formerly it is known as the ‘2019 Novel Corona Virus’. ‘CO’ represents Corona, ‘VI’ states for the virus, ‘D’ for disease, which outbreak in the 2019 year, Therefore, official name has been announced by WHO Corona Virus Disease (Covid -19). As per WHO the official virus name is known as severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus -2 (SARS-CoV-2). Viruses are named based on their genetic structure to facilitate the development of diagnostic tests, vaccines, and medicines. The name is given by ICTV on 11 February 2020. This name was chosen due to the virus being generally related to the coronavirus that is responsible for the SARS outbreak of 2003. While related, the two viruses are different. Example: HIV is the virus that causes AIDS,ie,

SARS-CoV-2 is the virus cause Covid -19 disease. The first case was detected at Wuhan, China on 31st December 2019. In India first case was reported on 30th January 2020. Coronavirus is a large family virus that may cause illness in animals or humans. Similar family groups are MERS (Middle East Respiratory Syndrome) and severe acute respiratory syndrome (SARS). On 11 May 2020 WHO made the announcement Covid -19 as a pandemic disorder.

DEFINITION

COVID -19 is an infected disease caused by a novel coronavirus. It mostly affected the respiratory system. This virus primarily spread through droplets of saliva or discharge from the nose when an infected person coughs or sneeze.

INCIDENCE

Globally, over 177Million (176945596) people were affected with covid -19, in which more than 3 million (3836828) people died. In India,30Million people suffered from this worst disease and reported more than 3 lack mortality. USA and India have the highest mortality rate.

Covid -19 Pandemic Disease

INCUBATION PERIOD: 2 to 14 days

ETIOLOGY

The origin of the disorder is still unknown however most researchers are considered from bats.

RISK FACTORS

1. Weak immunity (autoimmune disorder)
2. long term illness of client (Cardiac, Renal, &Respiratory disorders etc....)
3. less than 10 years of age
4. old age
5. pregnant mothers
6. poverty and crowding

TYPES OF MUTATED STRAIN

- Alpha variant (B.1.1.7)
- Beta variant (B.1.351)
- Gamma variant (P.1)
- Delta Variant (B.1.617.2)

PATHOLOGICAL CHANGES

SARS- CoV-2 primarily affects the lungs (respiratory system) and damages the alveoli. This can lead to alveolar epithelial cell injuries with hyperplasia. Due to this cause secondary disorder like severe bacterial and fungal infection and develop complication like Pneumonia.

CLINICAL MANIFESTATION

- shortness breath
- dry cough
- tiredness
- aches
- nasal congestion
- headache
- sore throat
- conjunctivitis
- diarrhea
- loss of taste or smell
- rash on the skin
- discoloration of fingers or toes
- fever
- mouth ulcer
- coated tongue

DIAGNOSTIC EVALUATION:

The confirmatory diagnosis is the RT-PCR test (Reverse Transcription Polymerase Chain Reaction) (nasopharyngeal or oropharyngeal swab) and, the Rapid kit test (viral protein antigen test), also we can perform X-ray and CT scans.

MANAGEMENT

About 80% of people recover from the disease without needing hospital treatment. Around one out of every 5 people who get Covid -19 becomes seriously ill and develops breathing difficulty. The treatment includes medicine like

Antipyretics (Paracetamol), Corticosteroids (Methylprednisolone and Dexamethasone), Antibiotics, Low molecular heparin for preventing blood clot and Hydroxychloroquine for prophylactic management. Then supportive management like oxygenation, nebulization, steam inhalation, chest physiotherapy, dietary, breathing exercise, and hydration therapy.

PREVENTION

Covid -19 we can prevent with proper handwashing (alcohol-

based hand rub), wearing a face mask, keeping a safe social distance (6 feet), early

vaccination, improving the immunity, and changing lifestyle patterns.

CONCLUSION

Now founded more mutated coronavirus strain. Therefore, it is a herculean task for stopping disease However we can control the spreading of infection with proper technique. So, all of them stand together fighting against this virus, saving lives.

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